

Cobalti-ammine Chromates and Chromato Cobalti-ammines.

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Briggs (Trans. Chem. Soc. 1919, 115, 67) has studied the action of potassium chromate and potassium dichromate on neutral aquo-tetrammine and aquo-pentammine cobaltisalts and has succeeded in isolating some chromato-cobalti-ammine compounds. In the present paper the action of chromic acid upon carbonato-tetrammine and carbonato-pentammine cobaltisalts has been described. It has been found that the course of the reaction in most cases differs entirely from that observed by Briggs and the products obtained are mostly different. The following compounds have been obtained :—

been obtained by the action of ammonium chromate and ammonia upon cobaltous hydroxide in presence of air.

Briggs has also obtained by the action of potassium chromate upon neutral aquopentammine chloride, a chromato-pentammine chloride, from which by the action of silver chromate, he prepared a chromato-pentammine chromate with three molecules of water of crystallisation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Chromic Acid on Carbonato-tetrammine Cobaltic Nitrate:—Chromato-tetrammine Cobaltic Dichromate.—

4 grs. of carbonato salt was dissolved in 60 c. c. of water and to this was slowly added with stirring a solution of 2 grms. of chromic acid in 20 c. c. of water. A dirty brown precipitate was at once produced which was washed with water, then with alcohol and dried in a desiccator over lime and calcium chloride. It could be recrystallised from hot water containing a few drops of acetic acid, yield:—3 grms.

The substance was sparingly soluble in water giving a brownish-yellow solution which on heating decomposed with the precipitation of cobaltic oxide. When heated in a dry test tube the substance ignited suddenly with explosive violence, gave out ammonia and nitrogen and a bluish green inflated mass was left behind. Solution of the substance in water gave precipitates with barium nitrate, silver nitrate and lead acetate solutions; the precipitate formed increased after addition of sodium acetate solution indicating the presence of an ionogen dichromate group in the outer zone. The solution of the substance was found acid to litmus. The filtrate obtained after precipitation with barium nitrate and sodium acetate, became slowly opaque on keeping and gave a further precipitate of barium chromate; lead acetate also precipitated yellow lead-chromate from the filtrate. These facts proved the presence of a chromate group in the inner zone. On the other hand, silver nitrate and lead

acetate when added to the solution of the substance together with sodium acetate precipitated the whole of the chromate showing that the substance was readily hydrolysed in water into a di-aquo salt.

Analysis:—

Found—Co = 16.52, 16.64 ;

CrO₃ = 56.3, 55.4 ;

and NH₃ = 19.19 per cent.

Monohydrated chromato-tetrammine-dichromate (formula I).

$[(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CoCrO}_4]_2 \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires,

Co = 16.4 ; CrO₃ = 55.8 ; and NH₃ = 18.94 per cent.

The molecule of water was lost by drying in vacuum over sulphuric acid. Briggs (l. c.) also obtained a similar compound of the composition $[(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CoCrO}_4]_2 \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by the addition of a neutral diaquo-tetrammine cobaltic nitrate to a solution of potassium dichromate and by drying the product in air.

Dichromato-tetrammine Cobaltic Dichromate.

To a solution of 5 gms. of chromic acid in 20 c.c. of water, a solution of 2 gms. of carbonate salt in 40 c.c. of water was slowly added with stirring. The solution was filtered and allowed to stand overnight. A blackish crystalline deposit was obtained ; it was filtered and washed with water. From the filtrate a second crop of the substance could be obtained on further keeping. It was recrystallized from hot water containing a little chromic acid. The substance was dried in vacuo over calcium chloride and lime. Yield:—1 gm.

The substance when finely powdered was yellowish brown. It was moderately soluble in water giving a deep reddish brown solution which decomposed on heating. The solution was strongly acid to litmus. The dry substance decomposed on ignition with explosive violence giving out nitrogen and ammonia and leaving a voluminous greenish blue residue. Barium salt solutions gave only slight precipitate with the solution of the substance unless sodium acetate was added. But in the presence of sodium acetate the precipitation was immediate and complete and the filtrate was free from chromate ion. Silver nitrate and lead acetate solution behaved in the same way. It seemed, therefore, that the substance was either an aquo-compound or one which was immediately hydrolysed in solution into an aquo-compound.

Analysis:—

Found—Co = 12·84, 13·2 ;

Cr O₃ = 62·4, 62·4 ;

and NH₃ = 15·1, 15·2 per cent.

From the results of analysis the only possible formula is what agrees with No. (II) *i.e.*, dichromato-tetrammine cobalti-di chromate with one molecule of water of crystallisation. The formula for the alternative aquo-compound $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 (\text{NH}_3)_4]_2 (\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_2$ requires Co=12·1, CrO₃=61·5 and NH₃=14·0 per cent. whereas $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4 \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7]_2 \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co=12·82, Cr O₃=65·2, and NH₃=14·8 per cent. which is much nearer the experimental values barring that of chromium, the low value of which may be attributed to the partial hydrolytic decomposition of the product which could not be avoided even by recrystallisation in presence of chromic acid.

Action of chromic acid upon carbonato-pentammine cobaltic nitrate:—

Dichromato-pentammine Chromate.

To a solution of 4 gms. of carbonato-pentammine salt in 120 c.c. of water, a solution of 2 gms. of chromic acid in 10 c.c. of water was slowly added with stirring. A red crystalline precipitate was formed. It was then recrystallized from hot water, washed and dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid. Yield:—3.5 gms.

It formed brownish red shining silky crystals; sparingly soluble in water. Barium, lead and silver salts at once precipitated the chromate ion from the solution in the cold, the amount of precipitate increased on the addition of sodium acetate. The filtrate obtained after precipitation with barium nitrate and sodium acetate solution however became slowly turbid but rapidly on warming and gave a further precipitate of barium chromate showing that a part of the chromate ion was in the complex though loosely held. Lead acetate and silver nitrate solution precipitated the whole of the chromate ion even in the cold. The solution of the substance was acid to litmus and as the addition of sodium acetate solution increased the amount of the precipitate, dichromate groups must have been present in the substance. When heated in a dry test tube it exploded with the evolution of ammonia, nitrogen and water and a greenish residue was left behind.

Analysis:

Found:— Co=13.4, 13.42;

CrO₃=57.7;

and NH₃=20.4 per cent.

Dichromato-pentammine cobaltic chromate (formula III) requires Co=13.65; CrO₃=57.7; and NH₃=19.7 per cent.

The only other possible formula agreeing with the results of analysis would be aquo-pentammine chromate dichromate but this is barred out by the fact that a part of the chromate ion is undoubtedly in the complex as whole of the chromate is not removed in the cold by barium nitrate and sodium acetate solution. But from the behaviour of the substance in solution it can be asserted that it hydrolyses very readily in water giving rise to the formation of an aquo salt as shown below :—

On the other hand an excess of chromic acid solution with carbonato-pentammine cobaltic nitrate gave rise to the formation of a brick-red crystalline precipitate which was recrystallized from hot dilute chromic acid solution.

The substance was sparingly soluble in water and acid to litmus. The whole of the chromate radical was precipitated in the cold with barium, lead and silver salt solutions in the presence of sodium acetate showing that there was no chromate radical within the complex. Hence it was only an aquo-pentammine compound.

Analysis :

Found :—Co = 11.67 ; $\text{CrO}_3 = 59.3$; and $\text{NH}_3 = 17.4$ per cent.

Aquo-pentammine cobaltic dichromate (Formula IV) requires Co = 11.7 ; $\text{CrO}_3 = 59.4$; and $\text{NH}_3 = 17$ per cent.

Action of Ammonium Dichromate and Ammonia upon Cobalt Hydroxide and the formation of Chromato-pentam-mine Cobaltic Chromate.—

Freshly precipitated and purified cobalt hydroxide from 25 gms. of cobalt nitrate was treated with 20 gms. of ammonium dichromate and 250 c.c. of concentrated

ammonia, the solution readily became dark brown and a portion remained undissolved which was filtered off on the pump. A rapid current of air was then passed through the filtrate for about 3-4 hours; and the whole was left to stand overnight. A reddish brown crystalline powder separated at the bottom next day. It was then filtered, washed with water and dried in vacuo over sulphuric acid. It was further purified by dissolving in a large volume of water and then precipitating by alcohol. The filtrate on exposure to air yielded a further crop of crystals. The yield was quite satisfactory.

The reddish brown crystals obtained in the above way were sparingly soluble in water and the solution was neutral to litmus. Barium, silver and lead salt solution removed only a part of the chromate as insoluble precipitates in the cold; the filtrate after the first precipitation on warming with a few drops of acetic acid gave a further copious precipitate of the insoluble chromates proving that a part of the chromate radical was within the complex and a part without it.

Analysis:

Found:—Co = 17.95; CrO₃ = 44.23 per cent.

Chromato pentammine chromate

requires Co = 17.56; CrO₃ = 44.3 per cent.

The substance on heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave characteristic red crystals of chloropentammine chloride proving it to be a pentammine compound.

The above compound on recrystallization from dilute acetic acid gave a brick-red silky crystalline product which on examination and analysis was found to be an aquopentammine chromate dichromate.

Analysis :

Found: Co = 13.13; CrO₃ = 55.86 per cent.

requires Co = 13.25; CrO₃ = 56.1 per cent.

The residue left after the treatment of the cobalt-hydroxide with ammonia and ammonium dichromate, was extracted with water. To the solution strong ammonia was added when a yellow crystalline precipitate was produced. It was found on qualitative analysis to be identical with hexammine cobaltic chromate.

It may be mentioned in this connection that the action of iodic acid solution upon carbonato-tetrammine and carbonato-pentammine cobaltic nitrate gave rise to the formation of only the corresponding aquo-iodates.

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